

The role of librarians in the research data lifecycle

Sonja Bezjak, ADP

Academic libraries' support for open science in the European Research Area, Staff training days at the University of Ljubljana, 15-18 May 2017

Content

- 1) Who we are and what we do
- 2) Challenges in research environment
- 3) Librarians as stakeholders in RDLC
- 4) Social science data repositories
- 5) Feedback

Social Science Data Archives, University of Ljubljana

<http://www.fdv.uni-lj.si/>

- 1997
- National data repository for social sciences
- Depositors from all 4 (3 public) universities, private research centres, Statistical Office of Slovenia (8-10 research centres per year)
- 600 social science surveys
- cca. 700 users yearly (90 % education, 10 % scientific/research purpose)
- Member of [CESSDA](#)
- [International projects](#) (DwB, Foster, SEEDS, SaW, SERISS ...)

Social Science Data Archives = in Slovenian →

Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov (ADP)

- **Social Science Data Archives** offer access to data that are interesting for **social science analysis**, with emphasis on problems **related to Slovenian society**.
- **Priority** is given to **theoretically significant** and **methodologically well designed** studies, especially data gathered over a period of time and international comparative data that include Slovenia.

The ADP's data catalogue: <http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/serije/>

Data + metadata +
accompanying material

DATA DEPOSITORS:

- Formats
- Standards
- Consent
- Licenses
- Bibliography
- Cobiss
- ...

ADP

- Selection
- Added value
- Curation
- Access
- ...

DATA USERS:

- Search
- Use
- Tools
- Citation
- ...

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

- 15 CESSDA members
 - Austria - AuSSDA
 - Belgium - SOHDA
 - Czech Republic - CSDA
 - Denmark - DDA
 - Finland - FSD
 - France -
PROGEDO/Réseau
Quetelet
 - Germany - GESIS
 - Greece - So.Da.Net
 - Lithuania - LiDA
 - Netherlands - DANS
 - Norway - NSD
 - Slovenia - ADP
 - Sweden - SND
 - Switzerland - FORS
 - UK - UKDS
-
- 1 observer
 - Slovakia - SASD
(observer)

CESSDA's objectives

- To support national and international research and cooperation in areas expected to be of great importance in the future
- To facilitate access to social science (and related areas) data resources for researchers regardless of the location of researcher or data
- To provide large scale, integrated and sustainable data services to the social sciences and facilitate and support research, teaching and learning

CESSDA's main tasks

- Coordinate the network of European data service providers
- Promote the results of social sciences
- Facilitate researcher access to important resources of relevance to the European social science research agenda regardless of the location of either researcher or data
- Include further data sources
- **Provide training**
- **Promote wider participation in CESSDA**
- **Develop and coordinate standards, protocols and professional best practices**

CESSDA Service Providers

- Operational bodies in CESSDA
- Provide services in their country and contribute to the development of the consortium
- Important instrument for dissemination of data, tools and knowledge in Europe
- Must fulfil obligations as stated in the Statutes
- CESSDA partners or linked third parties in H2020 projects aiming to strengthen and widening its services
- Link between the national and the international services

CESSDA's European projects

cessda saw

RISCAPE

- Strengthening and widening the European infrastructure for social science data archives
- A cluster project aiming at tackling important socio-economic challenges for Europe
- Dealing with new technologies in ICT infrastructure building for big data management and data manipulation for the societal challenges that Europe is facing
- European Research Infrastructures in the International Landscape

CESSDA Organisational Chart

Expertise, services, infrastructure...

... in social sciences exist all over Europe but researchers are still not motivated to publish and share data.

LOSS OF DATA

Research data alliance meeting2014

THE FUTURE?

Research data alliance meeting2014

Open Data project in Slovenia (2010-2013)

1) 22 semi-structured interviews:

- researchers, librarians, heads of research institutes
- 10 research institutes, 6 faculties
- 17 research disciplines: physics, biology, medicine, civil engineering, archeology, social work, economy, musicology, anthropology, languages...

2) 3 workshops:

- Workshop 1: Problems and Solutions in the Field of Data Services in Slovenia
- Workshop 2: Policy of Research Data Management in Slovenia
- Workshop 3: Advanced Technology for Establishing Data Infrastructure in Slovenia

3) Individual working visits/consultations:

- Information Commissioner
- Intellectual Property Institute
- Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts
- DARIAH, CLARIN representatives in Slovenia ...

INFORMATION TYPES

- [OPEN DATA](#) Action plan for establishing a system of open access to research data funded by public sources (2013)
- [National strategy of open access to scientific publications and research data in Slovenia 2015-2020](#)

What we found out? Open data in Slovenia (2010-2013)

Regarding documentation, retention and access to research:

- Researchers have **different habits and views**
- Research institutes follow **unwritten rules and practices**

But mainly they face identical problems:

lack of knowledge, time and finances for dealing with research data,
extremely competitive scientific environment

[,OPEN DATA'](#) Action plan for establishing a system of open access to research data funded by public sources (2013)

What we found out? Open data in Slovenia (2010-2013)

Major barriers in achieving open data:

- 1) big **differences in the development** of data infrastructure and services
- 2) **dilemmas and fears** emerging from questions **related to law** (intellectual property, personal data protection)
- 3) absence of **culture of data sharing**
- 4) **absence of framework policy**, which would help in research data management

Researchers mainly understand that **open access is a must**, they are aware of disorder.

And express the need of developing a framework policy and rules by which the system would be justly organized and would provide service to researchers (data creators and data users).

[,OPEN DATA'](#) Action plan for establishing a system of open access to research data funded by public sources (2013)

Reality ...

SCENE FROM THE PAST ?

DATA SHARING

Research data...

PUBLICATIONS AND DATA

„...constitute primary sources that underpin scientific research and enable derivation of theoretical or applied findings.“

Štebe, Janez, Bezjak, Sonja, Vipavc Brvar, Irena (2015). Preparing research data for open access : guide for data producers. URN:NBN:SI:DOC-G0DPXMZ1 from <https://www.dlib.si>, p. 1

All you need is in the article...

YouTube ^{SI} Search

0:30 / 4:40

Data Sharing and Management Snafu in 3 Short Acts

 NYU Health Sciences Library

[Subscribe](#) 129

63,236 views

+ Add to ↪ Share ... More

👍 374 🗨️ 6

There is a need to...

- Raise awareness
- Share the knowledge
- Change culture of sharing
- Support researchers

New roles appearing

<https://libraryconnect.elsevier.com/articles/learning-about-research-data-lab-pitt-ischool>

Thus...

Collaboration of various stakeholders is needed:

- Political and funding level
- Institutional
- Research Offices
- Libraries
- Repositories...

Also common tools, standards, services,
infrastructure...

A new paradigm...

Open data is data that is free to access, reuse, repurpose, and redistribute.

<https://www.openaire.eu/opendatapilot>

Change in EU: Open access & Open data

1. Background – Extension of the Open Research Data Pilot in Horizon 2020

 Please note the distinction between open access to scientific peer-reviewed *publications* and open access to research *data*:

- **publications** – open access is an *obligation* in Horizon 2020.
- **data** – the Commission is running a flexible pilot which has been extended and is described below.

See also the guideline: [Open access to publications and research data in Horizon 2020](#).

[Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020](#), Version 3.0, 26 July 2016

How ADP as service provider supports RDM

- Workshops
- Webinars
- Brochures
- Discussions
- Consultations...

Štebe, Janez, Bezjak, Sonja, Vipavc Brvar, Irena (2015). Preparing research data for open access : guide for data producers. URN:NBN:SI:DOC-GODPXMZ1 from <https://www.dlib.si>

Also for librarians!

ADP's RDM Activities for librarians

- 2 one day workshops

→ 18. junij 2014, Ljubljana: [Role of librarians in opening up research data and managing bibliography of researchers](#) (also in EN)

→ 26th October 2016, Ljubljana: [Knjižničarji kot podpora pri načrtovanju ravnanja z raziskovalnimi podatki](#) (only in SI)

- Lectures at several different occasions

Topics shared with librarians:

1. Benefits of publishing and sharing
2. What is research data
3. Types of data
4. Research data life-cycle
5. What is DMP
6. ...

How librarians see their role in RDM

Q4 How do you imagine you could help researchers in research data management?

In general:

- advise, give information, suggesting literature, references... (3)

Discovering data sources:

- Help when searching for content, select of data sources, help in data citing (3)

Long-term curation and access:

- To support preparation of research data for publishing, I advice researcher to get in contact with ADP, to help digitalization of data ... (5)

Results of the survey carried out before ADP's workshop for data librarians, 26.10.2016, N= 12)

Librarians are willing to take part but...

Obstacles:

- They feel that they lack the knowledge and
- confidence to talk to researchers on this topic
- They are overloaded with their own work

LEARNING HOW TO ARCHIVE DATA

Indicate how strongly you agree/disagree with the statements

1. I understand the basic stages of the data lifecycle.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

2. I feel confident in my ability to assist researchers with their data.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Benefits of sharing data

For the public:

- Research findings based on existing data on certain topics can **improve quality of life**; in Social Sciences gaining a better understanding of the community is important, including building collective identity and eliminating prejudice, discrimination, inequality etc.
- Open access to data also introduces **savings** relating to public spending on research and education.

Štebe, Janez, Bezjak, Sonja, Vipavc Brvar, Irena (2015). Preparing research data for open access : guide for data producers.
URN:NBN:SI:DOC-G0DPXMZ1 from <https://www.dlib.si>, p. 2

Benefits of sharing data

For the scientific community:

- **New research findings** which can only be achieved by using and combining available data from multiple sources, e.g. studies of trends or international comparative research, studies of rare or small populations, meta-analysis.
- More robust research findings can be derived as a result of validating and through **further analysis based on data related to publication**.
- Increasing the number of findings by enhancing the number of users of the same data, with efficiencies gained through **removal of duplication of effort** and/or the need to repeat raw data collection due to a shortage of funds and time.
- Training of future scientists, **using research data for teaching purposes**.

Štebe, Janez, Bezjak, Sonja, Vipavc Brvar, Irena (2015). Preparing research data for open access : guide for data producers.

URN:NBN:SI:DOC-GODPXMZ1 from <https://www.dlib.si>, p. 2

Benefits of sharing data

For the data creators:

- **Future reuse** of data by data creators themselves **is made easier** if data are properly documented and preserved.
- Indirect benefits for data creator's **academic reputation and career development** include:
 - **increased citation** counts and wider **dissemination** of their research findings;
 - data may be formally assessed for **scientific excellence** and form part of researcher's bibliography thus adding points to the score of scientific excellence.

Štebe, Janez, Bezjak, Sonja, Vipavc Brvar, Irena (2015). Preparing research data for open access : guide for data producers. URN:NBN:SI:DOC-GODPXMZ1 from <https://www.dlib.si>, p. 2

Research data - definition

... „is defined as recorded factual **material** commonly retained by and accepted in the scientific community as **necessary to validate research findings**;

although the majority of such data is created in digital format, all research data is included irrespective of the format in which it is created.“

<https://www.epsrc.ac.uk/about/standards/researchdata/scope/>

Data varies by how it's...

... **produced:**

- observation,
- experimentation,
- simulation,
- derivation,
- compilation.

... **represented:**

- text,
- numerical,
- multimedia,
- model,
- software,
- discipline-specific,
- instrument-specific.

... **stored:**

- ASCII,
- PDF,
- SPSS,
- Excel,
- TIFF,
- Java
- ...

... **conceptualized:**

- life-sciences,
- physical sciences,
- social sciences,
- humanities.

Johnson, Andrew M.; Bresnahan, Megan M., 2015, "DataDay! Workshop Materials and Survey Responses", doi:10.7910/DVN/Z59C5Z, Harvard Dataverse, V1, UNF:6:vy9Xiuk88J008yo/E/SGrA==

Research Data Life Cycle

Data Management Plan

DMP is the process of planning, describing and communicating the activities carried out during the research lifecycle in order to...

- Keep sensitive data safe
- Maximise data's reuse potential
- Support longer-term preservation

Donnelly, M. (2014): [DataManagementPlanning](#). HORIZON 2020 and the DMP ONLINE TOOL. Seminar: Preparing research data for open access. Faculty of Social Sciences. Ljubljana.

Data Management Plan

A research data management plan describes strategies for the collection, storage, validation, security, preservation, and sharing of data where possible, throughout the data lifecycle.

(CESSDA, <http://cessda.net/CESSDA-Training/Research-Data-Management-Plans>)

CESSDA SaW Webinar available on – [Research Data Management Community Training](#) – 23-06-2016

Data sharing – various possibilities

Different channels

- web page (own, institutional)
- data journal
- **repository**

Different approaches of data publishing:

- self-archiving
- **peer-review**

Repositories with different scope:

- institutional
- general
- **disciplinary**

Different types of repositories:

- **certified** / licensed or non
- open access
- ...

How to select repository

1. Use an external **data archive** or **repository already established for your research domain** to preserve the data according to recognised standards in your discipline.
2. If available, use an institutional research data repository, or your research group's established data management facilities.
3. Use a cost-free data repository such as [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org).
4. Search for other data repositories here: re3data.org. On top of specific research disciplines you can filter on access categories, data usage licenses, trustworthy data repositories (with a certificate or explicitly adhering to archival standards) and whether a repository gives the data a persistent identifier

<https://www.openaire.eu/opendatapilot-repository>

In re3data you can search repositories by

- Subjects
- Content Types
- Countries
- AID systems
- API
- Certificates
- Data access
- Data access restrictions
- Database access
- Database access restrictions
- Database licenses
- Data licenses
- Data upload
- Data upload restrictions
- Enhanced publication
- Institution responsibility type
- Institution type
- Keywords
- Metadata standards
- PID systems
- Provider types
- Quality management
- Repository languages
- Software
- Syndications
- Repository types
- Versioning

How do you imagine role of a
librarian in a research
data life cycle?

Library supporting research data management planning

- Provides information about the availability of existing data sources.
- Provides information about options to deposit data in a data centre or data archive.
- Helps select an appropriate or recommended data centre or data archive.
- Provides information about open access conditions and advantages.
- Supports preparation of formal DMPs.
- Provides support with preparation of basic study metadata and documentation, author's rights, and explains other deposition requirements.

Štebe, Janez, Bezjak, Sonja, Vipavc Brvar, Irena (2015). Preparing research data for open access : guide for data producers.
URN:NBN:SI:DOC-GODPXMZ1 from <https://www.dlib.si>, p. 7

Library participating in promoting data use

- Provides information about accessioning datasets into a bibliographic system for the purpose of scientific evaluation and resource discovery.
- Provides data citation guidance.
- Provides information on datasets, modes of access and possible use at information literacy training.
- Provides information about linking data with publications and research projects.

Štebe, Janez, Bezjak, Sonja, Vipavc Brvar, Irena (2015). Preparing research data for open access : guide for data producers.
URN:NBN:SI:DOC-GODPXMZ1 from <https://www.dlib.si>, p. 15

Czech Republic - ČSDA

archiv.soc.cas.cz/en/about-czech-social-science-data-archive

Getting Started JIRA

ČSDA Czech Social Science Data Archive
Institute of Sociology

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Čeština English

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ČSDA Team

International Cooperation

Projects

Projects in cooperation

Projects archive

Data sources, research of standards, data quality and data harmonization methods

Social Research Laboratory

The CESSDA Project: Building a CESSDA-ERIC focal point in the Czech Republic

Preservation Policy

About the Czech Social Science Data Archive

Mission

The Czech Social Science Data Archive (ČSDA) at [the Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences](#) accesses, processes, documents and stores data files from social science research projects and promotes their dissemination to make them widely available for secondary use in academic research and for educational purposes.

ČSDA promotes the objectives of the [OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding \(OECD 2007\)](#) in the area of social science research in the Czech Republic.

ČSDA participates in international networks of data organisations and it is the Service Provider for the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA). The major objective for CESSDA is to provide seamless access to data across repositories, nations, languages and research purposes.

Lithuania - LiDA

www.lidata.eu/en/index.php

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LiDA
Lietuvos HSM duomenų archyvas

MOKYMAI

Metodologiniai mokymų paketai Mokymų kursai Mokomieji duomenys Seminarai

NEW DATA

- 2017-05-02
Lietuvos socialdemokratų partijos tarybos prezidiumo nariai
- 2017-04-06
ESS7, atrankos dizaino duomenys, Lietuva, 2015 m. balandis – birželis, 2 leidimas
- 2017-02-17
Socialinė politika VI, 2015 m. spalio - gruodis, 2 leidimas
- 2017-02-06
ESS7, žiniasklaidos (naujienu) tyrimo duomenys

DATA SEARCH

More ... **New** ■ October, 2011 - The first edition of the data and documentation from ESS Round 5 More ... **New** ■ May 11, 2011 - LiDA started search program by variables More ... **New** ■ June

About LiDA

LiDA provides virtual digital infrastructure where researchers can deposit, search, browse, make online analyses and download almost 300 quantitative and qualitative social sciences and humanities data sets.

Training

LiDA serves as a tool to increase methodological competence of researchers by providing methodological assistance and training by means of distance learning, organization of data confrontation and methodological seminars.

Data

As the National Member Institution at the Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR) LiDA also provides access to international empirical data resources for Lithuanian researchers at major science and research institutions.

Research

LiDA coordinates international data collection initiatives in Lithuania, e.g. European Social Survey (ESS), European Election Study (EES) and International Social Survey Programme (ISSP).

ICPSR INTER-UNIVERSITY CONSORTIUM FOR POLITICAL AND SOCIAL RESEARCH
A PARTNER IN SOCIAL SCIENCE RESEARCH
ICPSR (LT)

European Social Survey

ISSP

EES european election studies

© 2018 © KTU Policy and Public Administration Institute

Updated 2012-02-23

Denmark - Rigsarkivet

https://www.sa.dk/en/ data librarian

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ARKIVALIERONLINE

Find original documents from the archives online:

Choose type of record

Search

[Guide to Arkivalieronline](#)

SEARCH THE DATABASE, DAISY

Information about the National Archives' collections can be found in the database.

Enter the name on file creation or file series

Search

[Advanced search in daisy](#)

[Log in](#)

CONTACT US

Phone numbers and opening

GENEALOGY - HOW TO GET STARTED

THE DANISH SLAVE TRADE - TIMELINE FOR TEACHING PURPOSES

www.gesis.org/en/services/research/daten-recherchieren/zacat-online-study-catalogue/ gesis zacat

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gesis Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences

Deutsch Kontakt Hilfe

Services Research Institute

Search Search GESIS...

You are here: [Home](#) > [Services](#) > [Research](#) > [ZACAT Online study catalogue](#)

Online Study Catalogue - ZACAT

[ZACAT](#) is a social science data portal allowing you to search for, browse, analyse and download social science survey data. The studies in this catalogue present a small selection of the studies available at the GESIS Data Archive for the Social Sciences - however the ZACAT holdings are extended on a regular base. Beside documentation on study level (e.g. abstract, related publications), all studies come along with documentation of full question and answer texts on variable level. Moreover, for some of the collections documentation on variable level is offered in two or more languages.

The available study collections at ZACAT

- [International Social Survey Programme \(ISSP\) - web pages](#)
- [Comparative Study of Electoral Systems \(CSES\) - web pages](#)
- Eurobarometer:
 - [Standard and Special Topic Eurobarometer - web pages](#)
 - [Candidate Countries Eurobarometer - web pages](#)
 - [Central and Eastern Eurobarometer - web pages](#)
- European Values Study:
 - [Longitudinal Data File 1981-2008 - web pages](#)
 - [1981 1st wave - web pages](#)
 - [1990 2nd wave - web pages](#)
 - [1999/2000 3rd wave - web pages](#)
 - [2008 4th wave - web pages](#)
- [ALLBUS \(German General Social Survey\) - web pages](#)
- Studies from Eastern Europe:
 - [Comparative Studies - web pages](#)
 - [Election Studies - web pages](#)

France - Progedo

DATA
INFRASTRUCTURE

*Développer
la culture des données*

PROGEDO

PRODUCE

SHARE

PROMOTE

PROGEDO

The PROGEDO large infrastructure ensures the implementation of a public policy for social sciences and humanities.

- MISSION >
- ORGANISATION >
- GOVERNANCE >
- TEAM >

Belgium - SOHDA

TOPIC:

Data collection &
Data management

Social sciences and humanities data archive

Researcher: [Johan Surkyn](#) – Promotor: [Patrick Deboosere](#)

Partners: [Université Catholique de Louvain \(UCL\)](#), [National Archive](#)

2014-2016 | federal funding

Abstract:

Pilot year for the Belgian data archive for the social sciences and humanities under the European CESSDA framework – Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives. A Data Archive is a virtual space where survey or register data from the Social Sciences and Humanities can be stored, documented and made available for further research. ID will work in collaboration with BELSPO, the UCL and the National Archive to explore the alternative paths towards such a Data Archive in Belgium, in analogy with data archives in many other European countries. Furthermore, a new operational website will be dedicated to archived data originating from and beyond past studies carried out at both research centers.

CONTACT US

📍 Pleinlaan 2, 1050 Brussels

☎ +32 2 614 81 50

📠 +32 2 614 81 35

INTERNATIONAL PARTNER ORGANISATIONS

[Population Europe](#) >

[European Association for Population Studies](#) >

Italy – UNIDATA BICOCCA DATA ARCHIVE

- HOME
- DEPOSIT DATA
- ABOUT US
- HOW TO GET THE DATA
- ADVANCED SEARCH
- NESSTAR CATALOGUE
- SERVICES

- DATA
- NEWS
- COLLECTIONS
- Italy flag
- UK flag

Search Data*: [\(click here for the advanced search\)](#)

*currently only in the title and abstract of the data

RESTRICTED AREA:

[Login](#) | [Register](#) | To access the restricted area

Latest Data:

SN173

Italian Labour Force Survey – July (2016)

ISTAT

The Italian Labour Force Survey is the main source of statistical information on the Italian labor market. The information gathered from the population constitutes the basis on which official estimations [...]

SN151

Household Budget Survey (2009)

Latest News:

30/03/2017

Flash Eurobarometer study released by the GESIS archive

The GESIS Data Archive has made available new Flash Eurobarometer study, listed below. The data are freely downloadable from the GESIS website, following the DOI address listed alongside the individual [...]

14/02/2017

ICPSR Summer Program 2017 in

EUROBAROMETER

Access all the Eurobarometer data for free

Discover our services on Istat data

Romania - RODA

The screenshot shows the homepage of the Romanian Social Data Archive (RODA). The browser address bar displays 'www.roda.ro/en/home'. The page features a green header with the RODA logo on the left and the text 'ROMANIAN SOCIAL DATA ARCHIVE' in large, semi-transparent letters. Below the header is a navigation menu with links for 'RODA', 'RODA overview', 'Ordering data', 'Data Creation', 'Data depositing', 'Data catalog', and 'Contact'. The main content area contains several paragraphs of text describing the archive's mission, its integration into a global network (CESSDA and IFDO), and its organizational structure. A small inset image on the right shows a hand interacting with a futuristic digital interface. The footer consists of three decorative panels with green and black patterns.

www.roda.ro/en/home

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ROMANIAN SOCIAL DATA ARCHIVE

RODA

RODA overview

Ordering data

Data Creation

Data depositing

Data catalog

Contact

RODA is the national Romanian institution specialised in archiving electronic data collections obtained by social research.

The archive contains data collections accessible for the academic community and the interested public, for secondary and comparative analysis, under certain [access conditions](#) ranging from free access to some level of restriction imposed by owners.

The main goal of the data archive is to preserve these data indefinitely, and to serve as an intermediary between the data owners and data users.

RODA is integrated into a global archive network, being affiliated since February 2002 to [CESSDA](#) (Council of European Social Science Data Archives) and since December 2002 to [IFDO](#) (International Federation of Data Organisations). By these links, international data exchanges are enabled; through RODA, users have access to national and international datasets from other European data archives.

In december 2013, CESSDA has become an ERIC - European Research Infrastructure Consortium, a research entity pan-European priority, located in Bergen, Norway. Since our IT system has been recently upgraded, RODA is prepared to inter-o new institution.

RODA is now organised an institutional consortium, governed by the University of Bucharest, the National Institute of Statistics and for Quality of Life Research of the Romanian Academy of Sciences.

Eesti Sotsiaalteaduslik Andmearhiiv ESTA

**EESTI SOTSIAALUURINGUTE
ANDMEBAAS** :: NESSTAR @
ESTA ::

Andmearhiivi tutvustus
Andmearhiivi statuut
Kontaktinfo
CESSDA organisatsioonid
ESSO - online ajakiri

TEMAATILISED ANDMEBAASID

- A. Kõrgharidusuuringute andmebaas 2000-2009
- B. Eesti vanemad sotsiaaluuringud

ESTA LEPINGUD

- A. Kasutamisleping
- B. Talletamisleping
- C. Taotluse vorm

MITTEELEKTROONSED MATERJALID

- A. Eesti Raadio arhiivimaterjalid
- B. Tartu Ülikooli Sotsioloogiaosakonna arhiivimaterjalid

Tartu Ülikoolile avatud e-ajakirjad

ANNA INFOT TEHTUD UURINGUST

ANNA INFOT PUBLIKATSIOONIST/ANALÜÜSIST

Estonian Social Science Data Archive webpage in English will be completed soon. Old webpage is [here](#). Vana koduleheküljega tutvumiseks vaata [siia](#).

Croatia - CRODAS

ABOUT US GET DATA USE DATA MANAGE DATA DEPOSIT DATA CONTACT Q

DATA ARCHIVE FOR THE SOCIAL SCIENCES

 DEPOSIT DATA —			
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EXPLORE OUR DATA COLLECTION

Data catalog

Macedonia - MKDASS

https://mk.seedsproject.ffzg.hr/?lang=mk 70% re3data

ost Visited Getting Started JIRA

English

ЗА НАС ПРИСТАПО ДО ПОДАТОЦИ КОРИСТЕЊЕ НА ПОДАТОЦИ УПРАВУВАЊЕ СО ПОДАТОЦИ ДЕПОНИРАЊЕ НА ПОДАТОЦИ CONTACT

МАКЕДОНСКИ АРХИВ НА ИСТРАЖУВАЧКИ ПОДАТОЦИ ОД ОПШТЕСТВЕНИ НАУКИ

- ние безбедно ги чуваме вашите податоци -

 ДЕПОНИРАЊЕ НА ПОДАТОЦИ			
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ПРЕБАРАЈТЕ ЈА НАШАТА ЗБИРКА ПОДАТОЦИ ОД ОПШТЕСТВЕНИ НАУКИ

Пребарувај податоци

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12.05.2017

OPEN CALLS

- 09.05.2017 **Advance on study results 3173 Barómetro de abril de 2017.** [view +]
Barometer Indicators (April 2017): Indicators of political and economic trust and confidence in the Government/opposition system; ideological self-positioning indicator and voting intention and estimation series.
- 03.05.2017 **Advance on study results 3174 Indicador de Confianza del Consumidor.** Mes de abril. [view +]
- 24.04.2017 **REIS 158:** New issue available.
- 11.04.2017 The CIS is carrying out the eighth edition of the **European Social Survey**. If you have received a letter to your home requesting your participation in this survey, we thank you very much for your participation. You can obtain more information about the survey through the means of contact indicated in the letter and the following [link](#).
- 23.03.2017 His Majesty the King presents the National Sociology and Political Science Prize 2014 to D. Emilio Lamo de Espinosa y Michels de Champourcin [view +]

[ARCHIVE]

- 24.04.2017 **Notice** (BOE 11/13/2017) for the **Training scholarships for post-graduate** in matters of interest for the organism for the year 2017. **Proposed resolution**. New lists with error correction: **List of admitted students**. **Lista de Excluidos**. [view +]
- 13.03.2017 **Notice** (BOE 11/13/2017) for the **Training scholarships for post-graduate** in matters of interest for the organism for the year 2017. **Form** (Deadline: (BOE 11/04/2017)). [view +]

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ACCESOS DIRECTOS

- 2016 CIS **Publications Catalogue**.
- Access to CIS **Open Data**
- Access to Survey Catalogue bank data**.
- (ICC) **Consumer Confidence Indicator**.
- Accessing the **analysis OnLine** of Data Bank platform.
- Latest studies added** to the Data Bank.

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Disclaimer

A joint project by
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DATA DEPOSIT IN ADS

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EAST PaC

In modern democracy, voters should be able to use elections to control parties and politicians. Citizens lose control when their electoral voice does not compel parties and politicians to act according to the will of the people. Repeated free and fair elections are supposed to function as a mechanism of electoral control.

To evaluate electoral control, citizens need the right data on candidates, parties, and parliamentarians. In this edited book, we present a step towards electoral control by presenting the methodology of the East European Parliamentarian and Candidate dataset (EAST PaC). These data are the universe of candidates and parties who stood for national parliamentary elections in Ukraine, Poland, and Hungary from the 1990s to the 2010s. Candidates are matched over time, rendering a dataset that allows researchers to track the political careers of every candidate, from the thousands who never won to the few political lifers whose parliamentary careers are decades long. With EAST PaC, we can achieve new insights into electoral politics of Central and Eastern Europe.

This book contains everything that scholars need to use EAST PaC. We designed the book for regional specialists and non-specialists; for seasoned scholars of representation, accountability, and political inequality, and for those who are newly interested in these concepts. We hope to intrigue potential users of EAST PaC and to attract new scholars to study electoral politics in Ukraine, Poland, and Hungary.

This book is funded by Poland's National Science Centre (Sonata Bis decision number 2012/05/E/HS6/03556).

East European Parliamentarian and Candidate data (EAST PaC) are available only via Polish Social Data Archive (ADS) and can be downloaded here: <http://www.ads.org.pl/opis-szczegE.php?v=E&id=97>

The book *Towards Electoral Control in Central and Eastern Europe* can be downloaded [here](#).

Archiving of research data is not a new issue. Researchers have been aware of the need to establish such an institution for a long time. Depositing and providing the access to the database allows for the openness of the research workshop, which contributes to standardization of the research procedures and enriching the knowledge on social research methodology.

Data archiving and rendering them accessible via one institution allows the spread of measurement tools construction standards, including the rates of social phenomena measurement. It allows for their inter-subjective control and provides not only ready-made patterns, but it also becomes an inspiration for new research on the basis of the already existing projects.

Collecting information on the projects that have already been completed or are being conducted, allows for gathering information and data source for the execution of one's own analyses with the usage of the already existing data and basing on the projects that have been executed by the others. What is important, in this way one can avoid the duplication of the research, and on the other hand, the researches can be enriched.

Data archiving and rendering them to the public on redistribution basis is an outstanding auxiliary material, that can be used for educational reasons. The diversity of the researched issues, methodological concepts and the research results that any person using the data from Archive can take advantage of, is undoubtedly a valuable material serving to spread the social science both among the professionals as well as among those who just enter the world of social research.

New data:

- 25.05.2016 **Zdrowie, nierówności, dezintegracja społeczna (Mieszkańcy Warszawy 2003)**, IFIS PAN.
- 13.05.2016 **East European Parliamentarian and Candidate Data (EAST PaC) 1985 - 2014**, IFIS PAN.
- 12.03.2014 **Zoom na Uniwersytety Trzeciego Wieku**; Towarzystwo Inicjatyw Twórczych "E"
- 17.01.2014 **Struktura społeczna w Polsce: POLPAN 2008**; Zespół Porównawczych Analiz Nierówności Społecznych, IFIS PAN.
- 23.09.2010 **Polskie Generalne Sondáže Społeczne 1992-2010** (ISS UW)
- 17.01.2014 **Struktura społeczna w Polsce: POLPAN 2008**; Zespół Porównawczych Analiz Nierówności Społecznych, IFIS PAN.
- 29.01.2013 **Polskie Generalne Studium Wyborcze (PGSW) 2011**, Instytut Studiów Politycznych Polskiej Akademii Nauk.
- 22.01.2013 **International Social Survey Programme 2007** (Social Inequality IV), 2008 (Religion III) i 2009 (Leisure Time and Sports).
- 21.07.2011 **Aktualne Problemy i Wydarzenia** (CBOS) 2008

It often happens that the researchers limit the hypothesis set to the objectives that they have posed while planning their research. Making use of already existent sets of data allows them to reach beyond the objectives that had been posed before the research started. The access to the data provided to people who have not been related to the project, opens the way to new discoveries and verification of the hypotheses different from the ones that were posed as the objective of the research at the beginning. Therefore, the researchers should take into account such a possibility of making use of the data. Simultaneously, it allows for the enrichment of the amount of information on the social issues and consequently, broadens the knowledge on social life, which is a primary and basic objective of every research.

Giving the Social Data Archives at your disposal we do hope to have our contribution in the execution of these postulates. At the same time, we realize that success of this enterprise depends at the same extent on the work of the people responsible for the organization and running the Archive, as well as the researchers themselves, who deposit data with care for their quality and compliance to the international preparation standards as well as technical and methodological treatment of the sets and documentation.

The demands on the data deposited in the Archives as well as the standard procedures of their preparation have been described in "Social Data Preparation Manual".

Latvia

There is currently **no social sciences data archive** (DAS) in Latvia. The strengths and potentials for DAS development in Latvia lie in positive attitudes of researchers towards data sharing; previous experience of a data archive; positive future plans regarding policy setting for RDM.

Finally, there is a **variety of initiatives facilitating and/or providing access to social sciences research data for reuse**: there are university repositories; OA repository Academia in National Library of Latvia;

(CESSDA SaW T3.2 survey, 2016, not published yet)

Thank you!!!

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